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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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Students' Motivation in Learning English through Quizizz (Current Technology in ELT)

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Abstract. Encouraging students' motivation in the target language is quite complex. In many cases, the students face difficulties in learning English and are not often obsessed to learn. Research in ELT has found that certain media technology can help the students get more positive attitudes and become more motivated in the learning process. The aim of the research is to investigate the students' motivation in learning English by using Quizizz. The participants of the study were 12 students at elementary school who take an English Course. The data were taken through questionnaire and interview. Findings showed that learners are motivated to learn English by using Quizizz. Most of the students agreed and strongly agreed that Quizizz was implemented in their learning process.

Keywords: language learning, young learner, motivation, Quizizz

1. Introduction

Considering the importance of learning English, some students take an English course to learn English outside the school. It is also dominated by young learners, since the Indonesia government has abolished the English subject in elementary school. Nevertheless, it does not mean that English is an interesting subject for young learners. The teacher needs to motivate students in learning English because learning activities will run smoothly when students have the motivation to learn. According to Juniar (2016) both learning and motivation are important for students' performance. Learning facilitates students to acquire knowledge and skills, whereas motivation encourages students to learn English better. Generally, motivated students will be easy to achieve higher level in learning English. It is crucial to know whether students are motivated or not, so that the teachers can develop better teaching learning activities.

Harmer (2007) defined motivation as state of a cognitive arousal which provokes a decision to act. It pushes someone to do something in order to achieve the goal. Motivation is a significantly essential factor for academic learning and achievement across childhood through adolescence [3]. Am (2011) explains that students who have the high motivation is indicated by some characters, such as diligent and active in learning, resilience facing difficulties, showing interest in various problems, quickly bored on routine tasks, maintain his opinion, and enthusiast to find and solve problems. Considering all the theories above, motivation is crucial in learning process.

Many ways can be implemented by the teacher to promote students' motivation to learn. Since students are considered as digital natives and people nowadays live in a technology and digital

environment, it is important for the teacher to create more opportunities for the students to get inspired, motivated, and engaged in learning activities by using technology digital. Teachers should encourage students to use their smartphones, which most students will have it today, for doing something meaningful such as for learning.

Previous studies have shown digital technologies can be beneficial for students' learning engagement and motivation. Chang et al., (2016); Thang et al., (2015) said that the digital context can motivate students to apply positive emotion in awareness, retention, and improve students' performance. Related to young learners, one of the trends to get them motivated by the use of ICT is throughout gamification. It creates a new approach and technique to engage the activeness of the students in learning, improve their confidence, generate positive learning outcome [7], [8]. Gamification refers to the utilize of game-based mechanism and game thinking to attract students, motivate action, enhance self-regulation, maintain playfulness and happiness, improve learning, and solve problems [9], [10]. In other words, gamification is the use of approach and features as game thinking which is not similar in context from the games is.

There are some online tools for gamification which are available playing in the smartphone, such as Kahoot!, Quizizz, Duolingo, Quizlet, Wordwall, ClassDojo, and many more. Those are suitable for students and the teacher can see the automatic progress and result of the students in the learning process. This study focused on Quizizz which has been implemented by the researcher herself as a teacher who use Quizizz in the teaching young learners.

Quizizz is a fun multiplayer classroom activity, that can be downloaded and used free. Chaiyo & Nokham (2017) said that Quizizz is a game-based learning tool that can contribute to student concentration, participation, happiness, and motivation. Furthermore, Quizizz can be used as an online assessment tool [12]. Quizizz is very useful for student and teacher for some reasons; (1) Quizizz can foster student interest and participation in learning [13], (2) student pace appear on each students' screen, so they can answer question at their own pace and review their answer at the end, (3) teacher can get detailed class level and students level insights for every quiz and download the report as an Excel spreadsheet, (4) teacher can access thousands of public Quizizz around the world create with thousands of great questions on quizzes everyday.

Numerous researches related to Quizizz have been conducted for supporting this current research. Suo et al.,(2018) investigate the implementation of Quizizz as game-based learning in Arabic classroom in engaging vocabulary mastery. The finding showed Quizizz affects the students to be more interesting and more focus on learning English. Then, Priyanti et al., (2019) conducted an experimental research on the effect of Quizizz towards the eleventh-grade students' English in reading comprehension. The research findings proved that the the Mean score of experimental group was higher than the control group ($83.08 > 80.77$). It meant Quizizz affected students reading comprehension. Lestari (2019) also conducted a research to know which E-learning application is better to boost up the university students' motivation by comparing the use of Kahoot! and Quizizz in teaching learning process. The result showed that mostly students stated that Quizizz was more attractive, challenging and motivating than Kahoot!.

Based on the consideration above, eventhough the studies have revealed that implementation of Quizizz is beneficial for students' skill and motivation, this present study is still important to conduct because those researches addressed at students in formal school and the participant mostly are teenagers and adult learners. Whereas, this study focused on investigating the student's motivation of young learners who takes an English Course. The students do not get the subject at school and do not recognise the aim of studying; English is new for them, those lead the students are lack of motivation and enthusiasm during learning activity. So, the teacher should ensure interesting instructions to be applied, the possible one is by using Quizizz.

2. Research Method

The research design is qualitative research method concerning phenomenological study. According to Ary et al., (2010) qualitative research method is research method that focuses on understanding social phenomena from perspective of the human in natural place. They added that a phenomenological study is designed to describe and interpret an experience by determining the meaning of it as perceived by the people who have participated. Thus, the present study seeks to detect the students' motivation on the use of Quizizz in learning English.

The study was conducted in the English Course for young learners. Students have class meeting three times a week for 60 minutes. In collecting the data, the researcher distributed questionnaire to twelve students attending the English Course. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted individually and face-to-face that only asked five selected students at random. The students who involved in this study are between the ages of 10 and 12. Our sample is purposive because it serves the objectives of our study to gain insight in the selected phenomenon [18] that is the motivation of students using Quizizz during the English language course.

The questionnaire was administered to figure out students' motivation towards the use of online learning platforms, namely; Quizizz. The questionnaire was adapted from similar previous studies conducted by [19]. There are ten questions on the questioners using 5 point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. The statements were designed to elicit participants' agreement or disagreement. Participants were instructed to circle the response that best corresponded to their level of agreement per each statement. Participants were asked to rate all items in the questionnaire on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – strongly disagree to 5 – strongly agree for items which express (1 = I strongly disagree; 2 = I disagree; 3 = I have no idea (neutral); 4 = I agree; 5 = I strongly agree) .

Meanwhile, interview was conducted to 5 students. The interview aimed to gain in-depth explanation and description on the use of Quizizz. Furthermore, the interview held to investigate students' opinion about their reasons related to the questions in the questionnaires. The data from the questionnaire and interview were used to provide description of students' motivation on the use of Quizizz. In addition, since the students were young learners and they learned basic English, the researcher designed the questionnaire in the form of Bahasa Indonesia, and guide the students step by step in answering the questionnaires without intervening their answer.

3. Result and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings related to the research questions on students' motivation on the use of Quizizz. In order to answer research questions, the findings from students' questionnaire is shown in Table 1

Table 1. Student's motivation on the use of Quizizz

No	Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Do you agree if the learning Based on Games implemented in English course?	66,6 %	33,3%	-	-	-
2	Would you be happy if learning English based on Quizizz?	16,6%	66,6 %	16,6%	-	-
3	Are you motivated to learn English using Quizizz?	25 %	50 %	25 %	-	-
4	Does Quizizz help you understand English more easily?	-	33,3%	41,6 %	25 %	
5	Is the application Quizizz useful for you to learn English?	25 %	50 %	25 %	-	-
6	Does Quizizz help you acquire vocabulary ?	8,3 %	50 %	25%	16,6 %	-

7	Does Quizizz make you being diligent do the assignment/ test?	16,6%	66, 6 %	16,6%	-	-
8	Does Quizizz more effective than face to face games?	16,6%	33, 3 %	8,3%	41,6%	-
9	Does Quizizz make your time more efficient in doing test?	16,6%	50 %	16,6%	16,6%	-
10	Is Quizizz easy to run?	33,3 %	41,6%	25%	-	-

It can be seen from the table that most of the students strongly agreed and agreed with the use of Games (strongly agree = 66.6%, agree = 33.3%) in the learning activities, and they enjoyed the Quizizz (strongly agree = 16.6%, agree = 66.6%). By using Quizizz the atmosphere of the class more fun and the engagement of each student was increase. Most respondents in the study agreed that that this application is interesting and motivate them to learn (strongly agree = 25%, agree =50%). The students also agreed that materials provided by their teachers in Quizizz help them in improving their understanding of the lessons (agree = 33.3%), however 41% students are neutral. Based on the interview, most students said that the features of Quizizz made them more interesting to do test and enjoy the learning, yet actually they quite did not understand the material. Moreover, the majority of students admitted that Quizizz was useful for them (strongly agree = 25%, agree =50%).

Furthermore, the table showed that students mostly agreed (strongly agree = 8,3 %, agree = 50%) that Quizizz can help them in acquiring new English vocabulary and be willing to do the test or assignment (strongly agree = 16.6 %, agree = 66.6 %). The students were more independently to do the test because each question and answer of students was shuffle and other features from Quizizz, such as its appearance and background music made them not felling stress.

Although there are students who were neutral and did not agree with question no 7 which stated whether Quizizz is more effective than face to face games, the high percentage still can be seen by the students who chose strongly agree (16.6 %) and agree (33.3%). Supported by data from interview, the students felt that face to face games can make them interact and collaborate directly with their friends. Additionally, most of the students agreed that their time is more efficient when they learned using Quizizz. Then, the students' response on time effectiveness and encouragement in practicing language skills were 50 % respondents agree and strongly agree were 16.6 % with the statement that the use of Quizizz saves time in learning and doing the test. Majority of the respondents strongly agree (33.3 %) and agree (41,6 %) that the students thought Quizizz is easy to use especially in doing their test.

Considering the finding in this research, it can be seen that the implementation of Quizizz affected the participation and motivation of students in learning process or doing the tests. It was seen that the result of this research was Agree with the implementation of Quizizz in fostering their motivation to learn English. Those findings are relevant to research findings of Basuki & Hidayati (2019) which concluded Quizizz is more more entertaining and more engaging.

Moreover, Quizizz considered as one of evaluation tools that facilitating assignment or test to the students. It can be an alternative effective assessment tool in learning language. Many students feel that online test by using Quizizz can reduce their fearful during the test. It is supported by the result of the study that quiz games can reduce students' anxiety [21]. Moreover, students found that submitting their assignment or test Quizizz is quite easy. Besides, it does not require much time and effort.

In addition, the findings showed that working with technology will make students learn more quickly, and are better motivated to learn. This is in line with the results of the research by Bury (2017) which states using media technology can improve students' motivation. Many students accept that while playing a game, they feel interesting to learn.

4. Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the questionnaires and interview, the implementation of Quizizz was interesting and affecting students' motivation to do the test on their learning process. The students enjoyed during the learning activities by using Quizizz. Therefore, it can be concluded that the use of Quizizz in learning English

can increase students' motivation. Thus, it can be explored as a supplementary learning tool. By integrating Quizizz in learning, the students do not feel bored and experience new learning atmosphere. Whereas, the implementation of Quizizz help the teachers to conduct the test in the classroom easily and teacher can make students more motivated in learning process by using this applications. Hence, the teachers have to be more creative in helping students to achieve the learning objectives. Finally, further studies are suggested to be conducted involving more participants or different areas in the context of EFL students.

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